

Digital Experiential Marketing and Repurchase Intentions Among Generation Z in Morocco: An Extended Theory of Planned Behavior Approach.

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Abstract

Gen Z (ages 15 to 24) in Morocco makes up 16.2% of the population and exhibits behaviors distinct from older generations. They are highly tech-savvy, using the internet for work, dating, and socializing. Social media plays a central role in their lives, with 43% spending 3 to 5 hours daily on these platforms. The rise of advanced technologies has also transformed experiential marketing, which traditionally engages consumers through experiences that evoke emotions, perceptions, and thoughts. This has led to the evolution of Digital Experiential Marketing, which uses technology to create unique, interactive experiences. The question is: how can this digital integration enhance repurchase intentions among Gen Z in Morocco? This paper will explore this question through a literature review of relevant concepts and a survey of 117 Gen Z individuals living in Morocco.

Key Words

GenZ, Morocco, Digital experiential marketing, Purchase intentions, Experiential marketing, Emotional connections, Interactivity, Consumer behavior.

Introduction

The rapid evolution of digital technologies has profoundly transformed marketing practices, giving rise to new approaches centered on customer experience. Among these, digital experiential marketing has emerged as a key strategy enabling firms to create immersive, interactive, and personalized experiences. This shift is particularly relevant when targeting Generation Z, a cohort of digital natives whose consumption behaviors are strongly influenced by online interactions and technological environments.

In the Moroccan context, Generation Z represents a significant and increasingly influential segment of the population, characterized by high levels of digital engagement and distinct expectations toward brands. Despite the growing adoption of digital experiential marketing strategies by firms, their effectiveness in shaping consumer behavior, particularly repurchase intentions, remains insufficiently explored in emerging markets such as Morocco.

The objective of this study is to examine the extent to which digital experiential marketing influences repurchase intentions among Generation Z in Morocco. More specifically, this research seeks to analyze the role of three key experiential dimensions, emotional connection, consumer engagement, and opportunities for interaction and feedback, in shaping repurchase behavior.

To address this objective, the study is grounded in the Theory of Planned Behavior (Ajzen, 1991), extended to incorporate experiential variables relevant to digital environments. A quantitative approach was adopted, based on a survey conducted among 117 individuals belonging to Generation Z in Morocco.

This paper is structured as follows: the first section presents the literature review and theoretical foundations of the study. The second section outlines the research methodology. The third section presents the empirical results and hypothesis testing. Finally, the paper concludes with a discussion of the findings, implications, limitations, and directions for future research.

1. Literature review

This literature review presents the results of a systematic analysis of over twenty academic papers that examine different facets of digital experiential marketing and the characteristics of Gen Z.

As a response to the gap in the marketing and consumer behavior literature, we conceived using an extended theory of planned behavior to identify the distinct characteristics of Generation Z before exploring the specifics of Digital Experiential Marketing.

Ajzen extended the theory of theory of reasoned action that assumes that one of the prominent antecedent of the individual behavior is the individual's intention which are in turn influenced

by attitudes and social norms (Fishbein and Ajzen , 1967). Subsequently, the extended Theory of planned behavior has been expanded by Ajzen, (1991).

Recent studies have continued to validate and extend the Theory of Planned Behavior in digital contexts, particularly in technology adoption and online consumer behavior (Wang et al., 2024; Dwivedi et al., 2021).

In spite of the panoply of studies focused on Digital experiential Marketing, we addressed the mainstream connections of emotions, feedback and interaction to examine GenZ purchase behavior. Subsequently, the use of the theory of planned behavior predicts successfully individuals' behavior according to a plethora of studies carried in different disciplines over the past few decades such as sustainability, advertisement, tourism, healthcare and many more, it has been enriching in different perspectives and contexts. This concept applies to various fields, such as technology, medicine, and politics, offering a persuasive explanation of how individuals adopt new ideas and practices. The theory of planned behavior is a concept that improves predictive power of the different beliefs aspects, attitude, subjective norms, control and intention (Ajzen., 1991). Therefore, it is an extendable and predictable theory of the individual behaviors performed depending on psychological metrics as intention, attitudes, subjective norms and perceived behavioral control (Ajzen.,1991). As a cutting-edge technology, the tpb was used to examine student's usage intention of generative artificial intelligence that showed a positive impact on AI literacy mediated by their attitudes and subjective norms (Wang et al., 2024). Another study has been conducted to show the importance of adopting technology for the usage of digital marketing tools and its impact on people's intention specifically entrepreneurs. (Phuong et al., 2023)

1.1 What is GENZ?

Generations are typically defined against larger traits that are a product of the time they are born in. There are the Baby Boomers who are a generation that grew in affluence and consumerism and still have enormous influence on their economies. Their successors, Generation X, saw and drove a shift in societal values; moving from the more family focused Baby Boomer mentality to one of self-actualization. Millennials witnessed the transition of technology from analog to digital and further heightened Gen X's sense of self-actualization becoming the "megeneration".

Finally, today's up and coming generation, are Generation Z; digital natives born into the era of social media.

Generation Z refers to people born between 1996 and 2010. They're the second-youngest generation, between millennials and Generation Alpha. Gen Z identity has been shaped by the digital age, climate anxiety, a shifting financial landscape, and COVID-19. They're known as

‘digital natives’: the first generation to grow up with the internet. They are the first generation to be born and raised with smartphones. This group is notably dependent on mobile devices, dedicating a significant amount of time to using their smartphones. The differences between generations have also brought shifts in consumer behavior. Priporas et al. (2017) suggest that Generation Z has a greater influence on reshaping consumption and production than any generation before them. Because of their reliance on mobile devices, many in this group frequently use their phones for shopping, appreciating how it simplifies transactions and provides greater convenience and flexibility.

The generation spans a wide range: The oldest Gen Zers have jobs and mortgages, while the youngest are still preteens.

Globally, Gen Z is growing fast. Morocco had 5.9 million young people aged 15 to 24 in 2021, accounting for 16.2% of the total population, according to an information note from the High Commission for Planning (HCP), published in honor of International Youth Day (August 12). According to the study "Maroc Connecté: tendances de la GEN Z sur les réseaux sociaux" (Connected Morocco: Gen Z Trends on Social Networks), carried out by SAGA, a Moroccan communication agency, in collaboration with Opinion Way Morocco, a leading multi-country market research firm, a survey was conducted in 2024 among a representative sample of 1,040 Moroccan social media users aged 18 to 29, Generation Z is highly active online. This group is known for using the internet to work, shop, date, and socialize. In Morocco, social media plays a significant role in the daily lives of young people, with nearly 43% spending between three and five hours per day on these platforms.

Social media is integral to Generation Z's identity, and their communication style is casual, direct, and uniquely personal. They are a generation that highly values do-it-yourself (DIY) culture. Having grown up immersed in technology, they are exceptionally adept with digital tools, expecting to use them seamlessly in both personal and professional environments. Research shows that compared to Millennials, Generation Z is less driven by financial gain, demonstrating a stronger entrepreneurial spirit and being more trustworthy, tolerant, and open-minded. Interestingly, four out of five of their favorite brands are tech companies, according to researchers (Schawbel, 2014; Dangmei & Amarendra, 2016).

They are abandoning traditional corporate jobs in favor of content creation and have even devised a new Vocabulary inspired by algorithmic guidelines.

1.2 What is experiential Marketing?

Schmitt described XM as a marketing strategy with a focus on customer experience, in which consumption is holistic, and customers are treated as rational and emotional animals, with the methods employed being ‘eclectic’. Wood (2009) examined 'experiential events' and seemed to

approach experiential marketing (XM) in a context similar to that of Schmitt. Wood described experiential events as ‘a personal occurrence with emotional significance created by an interaction with brand or product related stimuli’. Same (2012) defined XM within the context of its relationship to experience marketing. The author posited that ‘experience marketing’ is the strategic and consumer-centric marketing of relevant experiences that takes into account the affective and cognitive perspectives of consumption experience. In addition to research that has specifically aimed to conceptualize experiential marketing (XM), the literature provides various other descriptions of its nature. Examples include Yuan and Wu (2008), who described it as ‘a marketing tactic designed by a business to stage the entire physical environment and operational processes for its customers to experience’. Furthermore, Rather (2020) explained that ‘XM aims to generate comprehensive integrated experiences which possess the qualities of feel, sense, think, act and relate.

A broader perspective on the existing efforts to conceptualize experiential marketing (XM) highlights several recurring themes, outlining an approach that goes beyond traditional marketing methods and aims to evoke a more holistic, emotional, and subjective response from consumers. This view is supported by the work of Larocca et al. (2020), who reviewed 12 ‘definitions of experience marketing (also referring to it as XM) and demonstrated significant consistency. Most definitions specifically concur that experiential marketing leverages experience as a tool targeting multiple dimensions, such as perceptions, emotions, and thoughts, while placing particular emphasis on eliciting emotional responses.

1.3 What is Digital Experiential Marketing?

Digital experiential marketing has gained considerable attention in academic literature and industry discussions, reflecting its significance in contemporary marketing strategies. Several scholars highlight the core elements of experiential marketing, emphasizing the importance of creating memorable experiences that engage consumers beyond traditional marketing methods. Pine and Gilmore (1998) describe the concept of "experience economy," where businesses must provide memorable experiences as a core value proposition. This foundational idea is often extended to the digital realm, where technological advancements enable richer, multisensory experiences.

Lemon and Verhoef (2016) discussed how digital channels allow brands to engage consumers through various sensory stimuli, enhancing overall brand experience and emotional connection. The role of interactivity in digital experiential marketing is emphasized by scholars like Hoffman and Novak (1996). They argue that interactivity allows consumers to engage actively with the brand, leading to deeper emotional connections and greater satisfaction. This idea is echoed by other researchers, like Malthouse, Haenlein, Skiera, Wege, and Zhang, who note that

digital platforms facilitate real-time feedback and participation, making the experience more engaging and personalized.

Also, Various studies highlight the emotional aspect of digital experiential marketing. For example, Brakus et al. (2009) define brand experience as the subjective, internal consumer responses to brand-related stimuli, which can be significantly enhanced in a digital environment. Engaging consumers emotionally through storytelling and personalized interactions is seen as crucial for building brand loyalty and positive associations.

Finally, Digital experiential marketing is characterized by its reliance on technology to deliver unique experiences. Researchers such as Sundar and Marathe (2010) discuss how augmented reality (AR) and virtual reality (VR) provide immersive environments that allow consumers to interact with brands in novel ways.

The literature also indicates a strong link between digital experiential marketing and enhanced brand perception. According to a study by Sweeney and Soutar (2001), experiences that resonate with consumers lead to increased perceived value and, consequently, brand loyalty.

However, the literature review revealed a lack of consideration of the limits of the digital experiential Marketing, particularly in its effectiveness in driving sales, as other factors may be included in the purchasing decision. In addition, we attempted to use the extended theory of Planned behavior model by adding the emotional connection, level of engagement and interaction, due to the wide acceptance and successful prediction of behaviors and behavioral intention (Han, 2015).

Recent research highlights that digital experiential marketing is increasingly driven by artificial intelligence, personalization algorithms, and immersive technologies, which significantly enhance consumer engagement and decision-making processes (Hoyer et al., 2020; Kumar & Gupta, 2022).

2. Theoretical Framework

Based on the outcomes of the literature review conducted, a conceptual framework was developed for this study, as illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure N°2: Theoretical Framework

Source: Elaborated by the author

This conceptual framework illustrates how effective Digital Experiential Marketing can influence higher repurchase behaviour by focusing on 3 key elements: Emotional connections, higher levels of engagement, and opportunities for interactions and feedback.

Emotional connections: By creating strong emotional connections with customers, digital experiential Marketing improves brand loyalty; emotional connections are essentials in creating memorable experiences, resulting in a higher likelihood of reproducing the purchase action.

Higher levels of engagement: By involving customers in interactive and participatory experiences, brands can keep them interested in the brand, and guarantee therefore a reproduction of the purchase behaviour.

Opportunities for interaction and feedback: Enabling a two-way-communication flow through the interactions between the brand and the customers, allows the latter to feel valued, which enhances satisfaction and loyalty, leading to the increase of the likelihood to reproduce the repurchasing action.

Drawing from the literature review and the theoretical Framework, the following hypotheses were formulated:

Hypothesis 1: Opportunities for interaction and feedback within digital experiential marketing initiatives will lead to higher repurchase rates among Generation Z in Morocco.

Hypothesis 2: Higher levels of engagement with digital experiential marketing campaigns are positively correlated with increased repurchase intent among Generation Z in Morocco.

Hypothesis 3: Digital experiential marketing that successfully creates emotional connections with Generation Z in Morocco leads to higher rates of repurchase behaviors.

3. Methodology

3.1 Research design

To conduct this study, we choose to use a survey. Surveys allow researchers to promptly collect data from a large sample of respondents, making it easier to project the findings on a wider

population. Also, compared to other methods, they are most cost-effective, especially when conducted online. They enable researchers to gather substantial amount of Data within a relatively short period of time, with the lower costs possible.

One other advantage of surveys is that they are anonymous, therefore, participants feel more comfortable sharing honest and accurate information, especially on sensitive topics.

They are also known to be flexible, meaning they can be conducted in several formats (online, physically or by phone).

To establish this survey, we considered data from The ministry of Finance in Morocco.

The survey is divided into 5 sections. The first one being the demographics, containing basic questions to classify the respondents. The second one is related to Social Media and Technology Use, that contains questions designed to assess the importance of technology and social media for the respondents. The third section concerns Digital Experiential Marketing Awareness; featuring questions aimed at evaluating the respondent's familiarity with experiential marketing strategies. The fourth section covers Emotional Engagement and Digital Experiences, focusing on emotional connections and experiences.

The fifth and last section focuses on purchase and repurchase behavior, featuring questions that explore how digital experiences impact buying decisions.

The Survey along with the responses can be viewed at the Appendices section (Appendix 1 and Appendix 2).

3.2 Data collection

The survey was created using google forms and distributed online to 117 individuals belonging to the target group (GEN Z).

3.3 Sampling

To carry out this study, we chose to use convenience sampling. As mentioned above, 117 individuals were reached through this survey.

This sampling method is very practical, according to Etikan, I., Musa, S. A. and Alkassim, R. S., the convenience sampling is cost effective and time – efficient, and has the advantage of ease access to participants and is perfectly adequate for preliminary research.

3.4 Data analysis

The Statistical Package for the Social Science (SPSS) was used to analyze the survey responses. This software is widely recognized for its robust capabilities in statistical analysis and data management. By inputting the survey responses into SPSS, we were able to perform variable statistical analysis and tests: The analysis included descriptive statistics to summarize the demographics of the respondents and inferential statistics to assess the hypotheses related to the

research question. The following section will provide a detailed presentation of the analysis performed.

4. Analysis and Results

The analysis plan of the survey consists of several steps: First, a descriptive analysis will be conducted to represent the demographic characteristics of the respondents, including their age range, gender, occupation and location, as well as their social media usage patterns, the most used social media platforms, and whether or not they follow any brands on social media, and if they do, what type of brands they follow. The descriptive analysis will also cover the frequency at which they encounter ads on social media, and whether or not they participated in any brand-sponsored events or experiences online (e.g., live streams, contests, AR/VR experiences).

Next a correlation analysis will be performed to examine the relationships between key variables like opportunities for interactions and feedback, engagement levels, emotional connections and the use of advanced technologies with repurchase behaviour. This step involves calculating correlation coefficients to identify significant associations between the variables. Lastly, Following the correlation analysis, various regression analyses will be conducted to determine the predictive power of these independent variables on repurchase intent, allowing for a deeper understanding of the factors influencing Gen Z’s purchasing decisions.

Starting with Step1: A Breakdown of the survey respondents’ profiles was established, to provide a detailed overview of the individuals who participated, including several criteria representing their demographics characteristics: Gender, Age range, Location and occupation.

Figure N°2 : Demographic profile Breakdown of survey respondents

Gender	Male: 76%
	Female: 24%
Age range distribution	15-18: 13%
	19-21: 46%
	22-24: 41%
Location	Casablanca – Settat Region: 69%
	Doukkala- Abda: 2,5%
	Fès – Boulemane: 2,5%
	Marrakech – Tensift - Al Haouz: 2,5%
	Meknès – Tafilalet: 2,5%
	Rabat - Salé - Zemmour – Zaer: 14%
Souss - Massa – Daraa: 4%	

	Tanger – Tétouan: 2%
	Taza - Al Hoceïma – Taounate: 1%
Occupation	Both (Student and employee): 14%
	Employee: 8%
	High school student: 14%
	Unemployed: 6%
	University student: 58%

Source: Elaborated by the author

The Majority of respondents are Male (76%), while 24% are Female. Most respondents fall within the 19-21 age range (46%), followed by 41% belonging to the 22-24 age group, and a smaller portion is aged between 15 and 18 (13%).

The data reveals as well that a majority of respondents are University students representing 58% of the sample. High school students make up 14%, along with those who are both studying and employed (14%). The representation of only employees is almost 8%. Finally, unemployed respondents account for 6%.

As far as their location is concerned, the data shows a great concentration of respondents in Casablanca – Settat region, with 69% located in this area. Following this, the Rabat – Salé – Zemour – Zaer region accounts for 14% of the respondents. Other regions such as Souss – Massa – Daraa (4%) and Doukkala - Abda, Fès – Boulmane, Marrakech – Tensift - Al Haouz, and Meknès – Tafilalet (each at 2,5%), have a much smaller representation. Regions like Tanger – Tétouan, Taza - Al Hoceïma – Taounate are the least represented.

Regarding the Social Media usage of the respondents, it could be described as follows:

Figure N°3 : Breakdown of the survey respondents’ social media usage

Social Media Usage	1-3 hours: 41%
	3-5 hours: 29%
	More than 5 hours: 25%
	Less than 1 hour: 5%

Source: Elaborated by the author

The survey results indicate that 41% of respondents spend between 1 and 3 hours per day on social media, 29% reported spending 3 to 5 hours per day, and 25% indicated they spent more than 5 hours per day on social media. Lastly, a small segment of 5% spend less than 1 hour per day.

The most frequently used platforms are shown in this table:

Figure N°4: Breakdown of the survey respondents' most frequently used platforms

The most frequently used platforms	Instagram: 85%
	Tiktok : 46%
	Facebook: 38%
	X: 29%
	Snapchat: 19%
	Youtube: 67%
	Reddit: 10%
	Others: Twitch: 3%
	Others: Pinterest: 2%
	Others: Discord: 4%
	Others: Teamspeak: 0.85%
	Others: LinkedIn: 2.5%
	Thread: 0%

Source: Elaborated by the author

The data highlights a dominance of Instagram and Youtube, with respectively 85% and 67% of respondents using them, while 46% reported they used Tiktok, 38% indicated they used Facebook, 29% said they used X, and 19% mentioned Snapchat. Platforms like Reddit, Twitch, Pinterest, LinkedIn, Discord and TeamSpeak have lower rates (10%, 3%,2%,2,5%,4% and 0,85% respectively). The respondents were asked whether or not they followed brands on Social Media, and their Responses were as follows:

Figure N°5: Survey respondents' Tendency to follow Brands on social media

Following Brands on Social Media	Yes: 82%
	No: 18%

Source: Elaborated by the author

The majority represented by 82% follows brands on Social Media, while 18% do not follow any brands on Social Media.

We were also interested in knowing the types of brands they follow on social media; their responses are as follows:

Figure N°6: Distribution of the types of brands followed by survey respondents on Social Media

Types of Brands followed on Social Media	Fashion: 32%
	Technology and Electronics: 44%
	Beauty and Cosmetics: 9%
	Food and Beverage: 19%
	Entertainment (Movies, Music, Games): 41%
	Travel and Tourism: 19%
	Fitness and Wellness: 29%
	Automotive: 9%
	Home Goods and Décor: 8,5%
	Others: Lifestyle: 0,85%

Source: Elaborated by the author

The analysis indicates a strong preference for technology and electronics with 44% of the respondents saying they follow those type of brands, and 41% saying they follow entertainment brands (Movies, music and games). Fashion along with Fitness and Wellness brands are respectively followed by 32% and 29% of the respondents, food and beverage by 19% and tourism brands are also followed by 19%. Lower rates were indicated for the other categories: Beauty and cosmetics with 9%, automotive with 9%, lifestyle brands with 0,85% and home and Décor with 8,5%.

The table below illustrates the frequency at which they encounter ads on social media:

Figure N°7: Distribution of survey respondents' frequency of encountering ads on social media

The frequency of encountering ads on social media	Always (More than 9 ads): 49%
	Sometimes (4-9 ads): 29%
	Rarely (3-4 ads): 22%

Source: Elaborated by the author

49% of the respondents indicated they are always exposed to ads on social media, 29% reported being sometimes exposed, and 22% stated they were rarely exposed.

Lastly, the participants were asked to indicate whether or not they participated in any brand-sponsored events or experiences online (e.g., live streams, contests, AR/VR experiences). Their answers are exposed in the table below:

Figure N°8: Participation in online Brand-Sponsored events and experiences

Taking part in brand-sponsored events or experiences online (e.g., live streams, contests, AR/VR experiences).	Yes: 37%
	No: 63%

Source: Elaborated by the author

63% Indicated they have never taken part in any brand sponsored events, and 37% reported having participated to brand sponsored events.

The second step consist of hypotheses testing through the performance of a correlation analysis: We will determine the correlation coefficient to assess the relationships between the two variables related to each hypothesis. A value closer to 1 indicates a stronger relationship between both, while a value further from 1 indicates a weaker relationship.

H1: Opportunities for interaction and feedback within digital experiential marketing initiatives will lead to higher repurchase rates among Generation Z in Morocco.

The Two variables related to this hypothesis are: Interaction opportunities and feedback / Repurchase rates.

The correlation coefficient between those 2 variables is approximately **0.39**. This indicates a moderate positive correlation, however, the relationship between the two variables is not very strong. This coefficient also suggests a positive linear relationship between these two factors, meaning that as variable 1 increases, variable 2 tends to increase too.

Figure N°9: Variables and correlation coefficient of the first Hypothesis

Variable 1	Variable 2	Correlation Coefficient
Interaction opportunities and feedback	High repurchase intentions	0.385679

Source: Elaborated by the author

These findings are further supported by the responses to another question posed to the respondents regarding the factors that influence the repurchase behavior: the quality of the digital interactions was mentioned by 78% of the respondents.

H2: Higher levels of engagement with digital experiential marketing campaigns are positively correlated with increased repurchase intent among Generation Z in Morocco.

The two variables related to this hypothesis are: Higher levels of engagement with digital experiential marketing campaigns/ Repurchase intentions.

The correlation coefficient is approximately **0.26**, indicating a weak association between the two variables, although it may signify that as one variable increases, the other tends to increase as well. There is some relationship between the two, but not strong enough to indicate a reliable

or consistent relationship. Therefore, we can say that this association may be influenced by other factors and variables.

Figure N°10: Variables and correlation coefficient of the second Hypothesis

Variable 1	Variable 2	Correlation Coefficient
Higher levels of engagement with digital experiential marketing campaigns	High repurchase intentions	0.261699

Source: Elaborated by the author

H3: Digital experiential marketing that successfully creates emotional connections with Generation Z in Morocco leads to higher rates of repurchase behaviors.

The two variables related to this hypothesis are: Strong emotional connections/Repurchase intentions.

The correlation coefficient is approximately **0.27**, suggesting that as one variable increases, the other tends to increase too. While there is some relationship between them, it is not strong enough to establish a reliable connection. Consequently, this association may be affected by other variables.

Figure N°11: Variables and correlation coefficient of the third Hypothesis

Variable 1	Variable 2	Correlation Coefficient
High emotional connections	High repurchase intentions	0.27507

Source: Elaborated by the author

These findings could be supported by the responses to another question posed to the respondents regarding the factors that influence the repurchase behavior: the factor of emotional connections was mentioned by only 26% of the respondents.

The next step is to conduct a regression analysis, to deepen the analysis, confirm or refute the hypothesis, and understand the relationships between the different variables identified.

This type of analysis requires the definition of dependent and independent variables, which we will do for each hypothesis.

H1: Opportunities for interaction and feedback within digital experiential marketing initiatives will lead to higher repurchase rates among Generation Z in Morocco.

Figure N°12: Independent and dependent Variables of the first Hypothesis

Independent Variable (X)	Dependent variable (Y)
Opportunities for interaction and feedback	High repurchase intentions

Source: Elaborated by the author

Figure N°13: Regression Statistics summary table of the first Hypothesis

Regression Statistics	
Multiple Coefficient of Determination	0,425134513
R-squared Coefficient	0,180739354
Adjusted R-squared Coefficient	0,173615349
Standard Error	0,880752551
Observations	117

Source: Elaborated by the author

Multiple Coefficient of Determination (R): This value of 0,4251 represents the correlation and indicates the strength and direction of the linear relationship between the Opportunities for interaction and feedback and the high repurchase intentions as an independent variable. It shows a moderate positive linear relationship.

R-squared Coefficient: The R-squared value (18%) indicates that 18% of the variance in the dependent variable (High repurchase intentions) is explained by the independent variable (Opportunities for interaction and feedback); Here, it's relatively low, suggesting that the model may not explain much of the variability in the Data.

Adjusted R-squared Coefficient: The adjusted R-squared compensates for the number of predictors in the model and is typically more conservative than R-squared. Here, it's slightly lower than the R-squared value, reflecting that adding more variables might not improve the model's fit.

Standard Error: The standard error measures the average distance that the observed values fall from the regression line. Here, a value of 0.88 means the predictions are exact and indicate a good model accuracy.

Observations: This reflects the sample size. With 117 observations, the sample is of a reasonable size.

Figure N°14: Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) summary table of the first Hypothesis

Analysis of Variance	Degrees of freedom	Sum of squares	Mean Square	F	Critical F value
Regression	1	19,6805075	19,6805075	25,3704677	1,7718E-06
Residuals	116	89,2083814	0,77572506		

Total	117	108,88888	9			
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Source: Elaborated by the author

Degrees of Freedom:

Regression: Since there is one independent variable, the degrees of freedom for regression is 1.

Residuals: This is calculated as the total number of observations (117) minus the degrees of freedom of the regression (1), giving 116.

Sum of Squares:

Regression Sum of Squares: This represents the variance in the dependent variable (High repurchase intentions) explained by the regression model. It indicates how well the model's predictions match the actual data. Since the $SS = 19,6805075$, we can say that the variable X explains well the variable Y.

Residual Sum of Squares: This shows the variance in the dependent variable (High repurchase intentions) that the model does not explain.

Total Sum of Squares: This is the sum of regression and residual sums of squares, representing the total variance in the data.

Critical F Value: Since the calculated F value (25,3704677) is much larger than the critical F value (1,7718E-06), we can reject the null hypothesis, suggesting that there is a statistically significant relationship between the independent variable (Opportunities for interaction and feedback) and the dependent variable (High repurchase intentions).

Additionally, the extremely low p-value (in the range of 3.27277E-083.27277E-083.27277E-08) further supports the conclusion that the relationship is significant, indicating that the probability of observing such an F value under the null hypothesis is virtually zero.

Figure N°15: Regression coefficients and confidence intervals table of the first Hypothesis

	Coefficients	Standard Error	T Statistic	Probability	Limite inférieure pour seuil de confiance = 95%	Lower Bound for Confidence Interval = 95%	Upper Bound for Confidence Interval = 95%	Upper Bound for Confidence Interval = 95.0%
Constant	1,54994229	0,21561489	7,18847512	7,0751E-11	1,12285068	1,97703389	1,12285068	1,97703389
Variable X	0,31971944	0,06347531	5,03691053	1,7718E-06	0,19398707	0,4454518	0,19398707	0,4454518

Source: Elaborated by the author

Coefficients

Constant: It suggests that if Variable X is zero, the expected value of the dependent variable is approximately 1.549.

Variable X: This coefficient indicates that for each unit increase in X (Opportunities for interaction and feedback) , the dependent variable (High repurchase intentions) is expected to increase by approximately 0.3197 units, holding other factors constant. This positive coefficient suggests a direct relationship between Opportunities for interaction and feedback and the dependent variable (High repurchase intentions).

Standard Error: The standard error for the constant is 0.2156, and for X is 0.063, it measures the accuracy of the coefficients. Smaller values indicate more precise estimates.

T Statistic: These values test whether the coefficients significantly differ from Zero. Higher values indicate a significant relationship.

Probability (p-value): Both p-values are extremely low, far below the common significance level (e.g., 0.05), meaning that both the constant and Variable X are statistically significant.

Confidence Intervals (95%)

Constant: [1.1229, 1.9770] Variable X: [0.1940, 0.4455]

These intervals provide a range within which we can be 95% confident the true coefficient values lie. Since neither interval contains zero, it further supports that both coefficients are statistically significant and that the relationship is positive.

Overall, there is a meaningful, positive relationship between Opportunities for interaction and feedback as the independent variable and High repurchase intentions as the dependent variable, supporting the validity of opportunities for interaction and feedback as a variable as an influential predictor in the model.

H2: Higher levels of engagement with digital experiential marketing campaigns are positively correlated with increased repurchase intent among Generation Z in Morocco.

Figure N°16: Independent and dependent Variables of the second Hypothesis

Independent Variable (X)	Dependent variable (Y)
Higher levels of engagement with digital experiential marketing campaigns	High repurchase intentions

Source: Elaborated by the author

Figure N°17: Regression Statistics summary table of the second Hypothesis

Regression Statistics	
Multiple Coefficient of Determination	0,483823944
R-squared Coefficient	0,234085609
Adjusted R-squared Coefficient	0,227425484
Standard Error	1,132375081
Observations	117

Source: Elaborated by the author

Multiple Coefficient of Determination (R): The value of 0.483 shows a moderate correlation between the independent variable (Higher levels of engagement with digital experiential marketing campaigns) and the dependent variable (High repurchase intentions), indicating a reasonable relationship.

R-squared Coefficient: This indicates that the independent variable (Higher levels of engagement with digital experiential marketing campaigns) explains about 23.4% of the variation in the dependent variable (High repurchase intentions). While still relatively low, it suggests that the model captures a meaningful portion of the variability.

Adjusted R-squared Coefficient: This value (22.7%) suggests that the model's fit is not significantly impacted by the number of predictors, reinforcing that the main variable still contributes to explaining the outcome.

Standard Error: Here, a value of 1.1324 suggests some dispersion around the regression line.

Observations: This reflects the sample size. With 117 observations, the sample is of a reasonable size.

Figure N°18: Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) summary table of the second Hypothesis

Analysis of Variance	Degrees of freedom	Sum of squares	Mean Square	F	Critical F value
Regression	1	45,06848229	45,06848229	35,14732893	3,27277E-08
Residuals	116	147,4614322	1,282273324		
Total	117	192,5299145			

Source: Elaborated by the author

Degrees of Freedom:

Regression: Since there is one independent variable, the degrees of freedom for regression is 1.

Residuals: This is calculated as the total number of observations (117) minus the degrees of freedom of the regression (1), giving 116.

Sum of Squares:

Regression Sum of Squares: $SS = 45,06848229$, is the variation explained by the independent variable.

Critical F Value: Since the calculated F value (35.1473) is much larger than the critical F value (3,27277E-08), we can reject the null hypothesis, suggesting that there is a statistically significant relationship between the independent variable (Higher levels of engagement with digital experiential marketing campaigns) and the dependent variable (High repurchase intentions).

Figure N°19: Regression coefficients and confidence intervals table of the second Hypothesis

	Coefficients	Standard Error	T Statistic	Probability	Limite inférieure pour seuil de confiance = 95%	Lower Bound for Confidence Interval = 95%	Upper Bound for Confidence Interval = 95%	Upper Bound for Confidence Interval = 95.0%
Constant	1,266719274	0,333717392	3,795784415	0,000236532	0,605689348	1,9277492	0,605689348	1,9277492
Variable X	0,509962517	0,086018545	5,928518275	3,27277E-08	0,339576334	0,6803487	0,339576334	0,6803487

Source: Elaborated by the author

Coefficients

Constant: It suggests that if Variable X is zero, the expected value of the dependent variable is approximately 1.267

Variable X: This coefficient indicates that for each one-unit increase in Variable X (Higher levels of engagement with digital experiential marketing campaigns), the dependent variable (High repurchase intentions) is expected to increase by approximately 0.5100, assuming all other variables in the model are held constant.

Standard Error: Here, both standard errors are relatively low, indicating a reasonable level of precision.

T Statistic: Here, both the constant and variable X (Higher levels of engagement with digital experiential marketing campaigns) coefficients have high T-values, suggesting strong evidence that they are not zero.

Probability (p-value): Both p-values are extremely low, far below the common significance level (e.g., 0.05), meaning that both the constant and Variable X are statistically significant.

Confidence Intervals (95%)

Constant: [0.6057, 1.9277] Variable X: [0.3396, 0.6803]

These intervals provide a range within which we can be 95% confident the true coefficient values lie. Since neither interval contains zero, it further supports that both coefficients are statistically significant and that the relationship is positive.

Overall, this regression output indicates a statistically significant positive relationship between Variable X (Higher levels of engagement with digital experiential marketing campaigns) and the dependent variable (High repurchase intentions), with a strong level of confidence in the estimates. The results suggest that Variable X is an important predictor of the dependent variable, making it a valuable component of the regression model.

H3: Digital experiential marketing that successfully creates emotional connections with Generation Z in Morocco leads to higher rates of repurchase behaviors.

Figure N°20: Independent and dependent Variables of the third Hypothesis

Independent Variable (X)	Dependent variable (Y)
High emotional connections	High Repurchase intentions

Source: Elaborated by the author

Figure N°21: Regression Statistics summary table of the third Hypothesis

Regression Statistics	
Multiple Coefficient of Determination	0,000970796
R-squared Coefficient	9,42446E-07
Adjusted R-squared Coefficient	- 0,008694702
Standard Error	1,043604728
Observations	117

Source: Elaborated by the author

Multiple Coefficient of Determination (R): In this case, it is very close to zero, suggesting that the model explains very little of the variability in the dependent variable, which indicates a weak model fit.

R-squared Coefficient: This low R-squared value of 9.42446E-07, which is equivalent to 0.000000942446, is further confirming that the model has little explanatory power.

Adjusted R-squared Coefficient: A negative Adjusted R² indicates that the model does not fit the data well.

Standard Error: A standard error of this magnitude suggests that the model's predictions may be quite dispersed from the actual values, which is consistent with the low R² values.

Figure N°22: Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) summary table of the third Hypothesis

Analysis of Variance	Degrees of freedom	Sum of squares	Mean Square	F	Critical F value
Regression	1	0,00011804	0,00011804	0,00010838	0,9917117
Residuals	116	125,247745	1,08911083		
Total	117	125,247863			

Source: Elaborated by the author

Degrees of Freedom:

Regression: Since there is one independent variable, the degrees of freedom for regression is 1.

Sum of Squares:

Regression Sum of Squares: The sum of squares here is very small (SS = 0.00011804), suggesting that the independent variable (High emotional connections) explains almost none of the variance in the dependent variable (High repurchase intentions).

The critical F value: Since the calculated F value (0,00010838) is much lower than the critical F value (0,9917117), then, the model does not explain any significant part of the variance.

Figure N°23: Regression coefficients and confidence intervals table of the third Hypothesis

	Coefficients	Standard Error	T Statistic	Probability	Limite inférieure pour seuil de confiance = 95%	Lower Bound for Confidence Interval = 95%	Upper Bound for Confidence Interval = 95%	Upper Bound for Confidence Interval = 95.0%
Constant	1,494175122	0,17752477	8,41671338	1,2267E-13	1,14253272	1,84581753	1,14253272	1,84581753
Variable X	0,000657648	0,06317073	0,01041064	0,9917117	-0,12447141	0,12578671	-0,12447141	0,12578671

Source: Elaborated by the author

Coefficients

Constant: In this case, it suggests that if Variable X (High emotional connections) is zero, the expected value of the dependent variable is approximately 1.4942.

Variable X: This coefficient indicates that for each one-unit increase in Variable X (High emotional connections), the dependent variable (High repurchase intentions) is expected to increase by only 0.0007, assuming all other variables in the model are held constant. This small coefficient suggests a negligible effect of Variable X on the dependent variable.

Standard Error: The standard error of Variable X is relatively large compared to its coefficient, indicating a low precision in estimating the effect of this variable on the dependent variable).

T Statistic: The T statistic for Variable X (High emotional connection) is very close to zero, indicating that the effect of this variable is likely not statistically significant.

Probability (p-value): The P-value for Variable X (High emotional connection) is 0.9917, much higher than 0.050, indicating that variable X is not statistically significant.

Confidence Intervals (95%)

Constant: [1.1425, 1.8458] Variable X: [-0.1245, 0.1258]

The confidence intervals provide a range within which we are 95% confident that the true parameter lies. The interval for Variable X includes zero, further confirming that it is not significantly different from zero.

Overall, these regression statistics suggest that the model has a poor fit to the data, and the independent variables included do not explain the variance in the dependent variable effectively.

Further analysis might involve examining other independent variables, exploring non-linear relationships, or considering different modeling approaches to improve the fit.

1. Discussion

Through this study, we wanted to investigate the elements of digital experiential marketing, that truly influence Gen Z, and drive their buying behaviors, we were able to verify or refute the hypotheses initially established:

Hypothesis 1: We can confirm that Opportunities for interaction and feedback within digital experiential marketing initiatives will lead to higher repurchase rates among Generation Z in Morocco.

One of the results from the study is the positive relationship between opportunities for interaction and feedback and the probability of repurchasing. Gen Z respondents seemed to appreciate the chance to engage directly with brands, whether through feedback forms, social media interactions, or other participatory digital experiences.

Hypothesis 2: We can slightly confirm that higher levels of engagement with digital experiential marketing campaigns are positively correlated with increased repurchase intent among Generation Z in Morocco.

Higher engagement levels, including participation in interactive campaigns, contests, and digital experiences, were also associated with increased repurchase intentions, though the correlation was weaker than anticipated. This may suggest that while Gen Z values interactive experiences, engagement alone might not be enough to drive repeated purchases.

Hypothesis 3: We statistically can't confirm that Digital experiential marketing that successfully creates emotional connections with Generation Z in Morocco leads to higher rates of repurchase behaviors.

The study found that emotional connections, did not have a strong relationship with repurchase intentions in this case. This could be due to several factors unique to Gen Z. Known for their pragmatic approach and high exposure to digital content, Gen Z may not easily form emotional bonds with brands simply through online interactions. While emotional connection is crucial in building brand affinity, it may not be the primary driver for repurchase among Gen Z, who may weigh practical factors over emotional appeals.

2. Practical implications

The limited influence of engagement and emotional connections on repurchase intentions reveals a deeper truth about Gen Z's brand loyalty: it is grounded in a rational, value-oriented approach. They are more likely to remain loyal to brands that demonstrate value beyond just an engaging digital presence. This generation places a premium on consistency, transparency, and quality.

For brands targeting Moroccan Gen Z or similar demographics, it may be effective to view engagement and emotional connections as supportive tools rather than primary drivers of loyalty. Campaigns that combine interactive elements with a clear demonstration of value can more effectively appeal to this pragmatic consumer base. By designing marketing strategies that integrate engagement and emotional appeal with a focus on product reliability, transparent messaging, and value alignment, brands can foster a stronger, more resilient relationship with Generation Z.

3. Study limits and future research

This study has several limitations, opening pathways for future research:

Sample Diversity: The use of convenience sampling may limit the representativeness of the sample, with an urban concentration that might not fully capture rural Gen Z behaviors. Future studies could employ random sampling or expand to include more diverse participants, ensuring

broader representation of Morocco's population and potentially highlighting differences between urban and rural digital engagement.

Additional Variables: This study focuses on specific aspects of digital experiential marketing, such as interactivity, engagement, and emotional connection. Future research could incorporate additional factors, such as perceived brand value or product quality.

Longitudinal Approach: A longitudinal study could provide insights into how Gen Z's responses to digital experiential marketing evolve over time. This would allow researchers to observe changes in repurchase behavior and brand loyalty as the cohort ages, potentially identifying shifts in digital preferences and purchasing habits.

Conclusion

This study aimed to investigate the extent to which digital experiential marketing influences repurchase intentions among Generation Z in Morocco, with a particular focus on three key dimensions: emotional connection, engagement, and opportunities for interaction and feedback. Grounded in the Theory of Planned Behavior (Ajzen, 1991), and extended to incorporate experiential variables, this research contributes to a better understanding of consumer behavior in increasingly digitalized environments.

From a methodological perspective, the study adopted a quantitative approach based on a survey administered to 117 individuals belonging to Generation Z in Morocco. Statistical analyses, including correlation and regression models, were conducted to test the proposed hypotheses and evaluate the relationships between experiential marketing dimensions and repurchase intentions.

The empirical findings provide nuanced insights into the effectiveness of digital experiential marketing. Among the three dimensions examined, opportunities for interaction and feedback emerged as the most significant predictor of repurchase intentions, confirming their central role in influencing consumer behavior. Engagement demonstrated a positive but moderate effect, suggesting that while interactive and participatory experiences are appreciated by Generation Z, they are not sufficient on their own to drive consistent repurchase behavior. In contrast, emotional connection did not show a statistically significant impact, highlighting a more rational and value-oriented decision-making process among this generation.

These results directly address the research question and reveal that, in the Moroccan context, Generation Z does not respond uniformly to all dimensions of digital experiential marketing. Instead, their behavior appears to be guided more by functional and relational factors, such as interaction, transparency, and perceived value, than by purely emotional appeals.

From a theoretical standpoint, this study extends the application of the Theory of Planned Behavior by integrating experiential marketing variables, thereby offering a more comprehensive framework for analyzing consumer behavior in digital contexts. From a managerial perspective, the findings suggest that companies should prioritize strategies that enhance interaction and foster two-way communication with consumers, while ensuring that these experiences are supported by tangible value and authenticity.

However, this study is not without limitations. The use of convenience sampling and a relatively small sample size may limit the generalizability of the findings. Additionally, the study focused on a limited number of variables, which may not fully capture the complexity of consumer decision-making processes. Future research could address these limitations by incorporating

more diverse samples, exploring additional determinants such as perceived value or trust, and adopting longitudinal designs to examine changes in behavior over time.

In conclusion, this research provides empirical evidence that digital experiential marketing can influence repurchase intentions among Generation Z in Morocco, but its effectiveness depends on the specific dimensions employed. A balanced approach that combines interactive engagement with clear value propositions appears to be essential for fostering sustainable consumer relationships in the digital age.

Appendices

1. Appendix 1: Study Survey

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